

Aetiology of piglet mortality, risk factors, and preventive measures

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Abstract

Piglet mortality is big hindrance in pig farming and pig Industry. The piglet mortality varies from 10-20% in farm basis. Mortality in piglets particularly upto the age of 60 days is a big determinant of success of pig rearing. Several risk factors are there for piglet mortality they are breeds, age, litter size, individual body weight, farrowing duration, litter size, herd size, parity, congenital defects, season etc. The causes also have wide etiological factors namely crushing, starvation, uninflated lung, infections, entry of birds and other animals in farm, anaemic status, still born, hypothermia, hypoglycemia, asphyxia, diarrhea and vomiting and other conditions. Several preventive measures need to be taken to restrict piglet mortality under single digit. Regular vaccination whatever available is needed, Iron injection as earliest possible in first week of age, adequate nutrition and supplement, avoid stress and adverse weather, maintenance of biosecurity, straw bedding to restrict exposure and injury, farrowing pen bar to restrict crushing and several other measures

Keywords: aetiology, piglet mortality, preventives, risk factor

Amongst the domestic animals piglet mortality is a unique as the piglet mortality may be very high if not checked at proper time. Piglet mortality rates vary depending on a number of factors, including the breed of pig, the age of the piglets, and the size of the litter etc: Piglets mortality varies from 16-20% depending on the different environmental and management practices. Sow farrows 5-16 piglets depending on the breeds. The farrowing time take usually 3-4 hours but sometime due to several factors the farrowing may take much more times. The extended period of farrowing indicates some pathophysiological abnormality vulnerable for piglet mortality in the later stage of growth. There are several several risk factors for piglet mortality after farrowing. Most piglet mortality occurs within 7 days of farrowing, followed by 2-3 weeks and

then 4-9 weeks. The vulnerable risk factors are as follow: -

Breed: Some breeds may have lower piglet mortality rates than others, Several breeds and crossbred show higher piglet mortality than native ones and feral animals. Pietrain, Durac show much mortality than indigenous breeds

Age: Piglet mortality rates are often higher in the first few months of life. Genetic variation piglet mortality maximum during first 12 days. Piglets' mortality including still birth, first week, second week and after second week upto 60 days are more. Piglet mortality in first week is highest (13%) than other age group (Thin. *et al*, 2022)

Litter size: Larger litters tend to have higher mortality rates than small litter size, this is due to availability of milk from sow for each individual piglets. Higher litter size there is competition amongst the piglets and the strong piglets takes much milk from sow and other remains underfed

Fig-1: Sow with 10 piglets some of which are vulnerable to starvation

Fig-2: Sow with 16 piglets (2 dead)

and subsequently anaemia and death (Fig-1 and 2).

Farrowing duration: Normally farrowing takes 4 hours but due to several pathological conditions, physiological status of sow coupled with environment factors the farrowing time may increase more than 5 hours or even more. Prolong farrowing time causes stress for sow and neonatal piglets that causes also some mortality.

Herd size: Usually small herd size show less post weaning mortality but some auth have reported higher herd size less mortality than nuclear herd size (Cokes, *et al*, 2021).

Birth weight of piglet: It has been found that sow farrows piglets with less body weight shows susceptibility to different infections and some of them eventually die later days. Piglets with higher body weight at birth were usually greater growth until two months of age. Daily weight gain (ADG) improves by increasing piglet birth weight between 0 and 21 days.

Parity: Piglet mortality rates tend to increase with the number of times a sow has given birth. In first parity less mortality than subsequent parity of sow

Congenital defects: Sometimes several congenital defect of piglets and sow uterine-vaginal abnormalities that causes death of piglets. Splay leg syndrome, congenital tremor, umbilical hernia, cryptorchidism, atresia ani, cleft palate, inverted nipple of the sow.

Numbers of teat: Usually sow have 10-14 teats and some time being polytocous animal more piglets are born than number of teats of the sow. Therefore, all piglets do not find teat to suckle for milk as a result weak piglets remain unfed and die of inanition.

Season: Piglet mortality rates may be higher in certain seasons, such as winter or post-monsoon. In winter months the mortality is much more than in summer and rainy season. If other stress along with season such as transport stress, heat stress the mortality may aggravate.

Cause of death: Piglet mortality is a big problem in the pig production. Several infectious and non-infectious causes are there that force to piglet mortality. Systemic involvement that leads to death of piglets are digestive systemic disorders, followed by respiratory, congenital defects, environmental factors and miscellaneous aetiologies. Piglet mortality varies from 12–20% die before weaning. Commonly following are some of the causes of piglet mortality in farm and free-range system

Crushing: Crushing means overlaying of sow on the little piglets, large litter size and weak piglets are sensitive for crushing. The sow can crush piglets, especially during the first week after birth. Piglets cannot properly estimate the movement of sow particularly during rest. This can be caused by the sow's behavior, such as restless behavior during

farrowing, feeding etc. During milk feeding to piglets the sow changes its posture that also overlays the piglets.

Starvation: Piglets may not have access to food, or they may not be able to adapt to the new circumstances after birth. Sometimes it may happen due to anatomical abnormality pigs cannot eat, even sow may be agalactic therefore early life of piglets find scarce of milk. Natural calamities like storm, torrential rain, severe winter exposure piglets are stuck unfed.

Uninflated lungs: Piglets may be born with uninflated lungs. In several pathological conditions piglets' lung remained uninflated. Pathological factors that may cause uninflated lungs such as lung atelectasis, interstitial pneumonia, highly pathogenic diseases like porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome (PRRS), Porcine respiratory disease complex (PRCV), several bacterial and viral pneumonia like Mycoplasma infections.

Infection: Piglets may die from bacterial infections, such as *Escherichia coli* (enterotoxogenic), *Clostridial defficile*, Coccidia infections, *Staphylococcus suis*, *Clostridial perfringens* type C, *Actinobacillus suis* (septicemia), *Salmonellosis* etc

Stillborn: Piglets may be stillborn due to uterine crowding or placental insufficiency. Several other infections like Aujeszky's disease, enteroviruses, eperythrozoonosis, erysipelas, leptospirosis, mycotoxicosis, parvovirus, PRRS, and toxoplasmosis also cause stillbirth

Birds: Larger and predator birds may enter into pig farm and may damage piglets by predation. Birds also transmit several infections from host to host.

Piglet anaemia: Anaemia in piglets common cause of retarded growth and mortality. It a deficiency disease of Iron, cobalt and other minerals and proteins. Speedy growth and less supply of Iron in feed and milk cause anaemia. The clinical signs of anaemia are pale, accumulation of fluid around their throat, brisket, and internal body space and diarrhoea. Mortality due to piglet anemia may be 10-15%.

Hypothermia: Hypothermia is a condition when body temperature downs from normal temperature. Piglets are susceptible to hypothermia because of their surface area to body volume

ratio. Hypothermia could be due to environmental thermal depression particularly in winter, sudden hail storm and rain, piglets are susceptible to poor thermoregulation and low energy reserve, hypoglycemia in weak piglets. Piglets are susceptible to hypothermia because of their surface area to body volume ratio.

Hypoglycemia: It is the condition when the blood glucose level become insufficient from normal (80-100mg/do) particularly in the very early life 12-36 hrs post natal. The main cause of hypoglycemia is insufficient availability of milk or feed, inclement weather in winter, low birth weight, inanition after birth

Asphyxia: Piglets can become asphyxiated if the umbilical cord ruptures, detaches, or is blocked. Causes of asphyxia in piglets are difficult farrowing, umbilical cord problems, advance expulsion of muconeum during farrowing and skin conditions. Consequence of Asphyxia leads to metabolic acidosis, brain damage, muconeum aspiration to lungs and hypoxia and may lead to death.

Diarrhoea and vomiting: Diarrhoeic death in piglet is very frequent. Diarrhoea causes dehydration and mineral imbalance, this affects the electrolyte imbalance that causes muscle and heart polarization and even cause death. The causes of piglet diarrhea are infection with *E.coli*, *Clostridium perfringens* C, *Coccidiosis*, transmissible gastroenteritis, porcine epidemic diarrhea etc.

Other causes: Piglets may die from other causes, such as electrocution, trauma, aneurysms, ileitis, hemorrhagic bowel syndrome (HBS), twisted gut, and stomach ulcers. In big farm causes of piglet mortality varies and the causes also wide. Piglets mortality due to overlaying or crushing is the most frequent cause of death (2.1%), followed by deaths due to diarrhoea (1.7%), anaemia (1.2%), cannibalism (1.1%) and losses of small weak piglets (0.9%) recorded by Spicer *et al.*, 1986).

Preventive Measures against Piglet mortality

Ensure that sufficient colostrums taken by each and every piglet which will provide immunity for general infections and humoral defense. Teat training may be given to piglet to suckle the teat. If sufficient colostrums is not available provide bottle feed with milk from other species and milk replacer. Maintain a warm environment so that weak animal particularly during very early age can get suitable

warm environment inside the incubator with remote sensing. This can be a good tool against inanition and hypothermia and hypoglycemia.

Adoption of Foster sow- Cross-fostering technique helps to move piglets from self dam to other sow to have milk etc, it prevents agalactia and inadequate milk replacer in early life.

Farrowing room hygiene – to prevent contamination hygienic farrowing room with disinfectants checks transmission of microbial to new born piglets

Early vaccination of pigs: The available vaccines may be provided so that antibody can be ready to fight against any outbreaks. Vaccines like Parvovirus, Erysipelothrix, Leptospira; Bratislava, *L.Canicola*, *L.Grippotyphosa*, *L.Hardjo*, *L.Icterohaemorrhagiae*, *L. Pomona*, *Clostridium perfringens* etc. Other vaccination such as PRRS, FMD, and Classical swine fever vaccine also be given as per need.

Iron injection- Iron deficiency anaemia is a persistent problem in pig industry, therefore needs to administer Iron from the first week of birth 200mg/piglet and repeat after 15-20days.

Provide adequate nutrition: Balance feed, vitamins and mineral supplement should be given so that no deficiency disease occurs either deficiency of proteins and energy.

Check harsh environment: Extreme cold, hot, stressful herd, wet environment, overcrowd, mixing of age group must be check. These are hardship for normal growth and invites infection and ill health

Maintenance of biosecurity- Potential threat due to infection of virus, bacteria and other microbes must be checked. Strict biosecurity measures decrease mortality rate and enhance productivity. Restrict unauthorized people in farm, restrict entry of other animals and birds in the farm premises. Isolation quarantine of new pigs and sick animals. Keep separate age groups separately. Regular disinfection of premises and fomites. Wear clean cloth and footwear to restrict spread of infection.

Use Straw for bedding- Piglets are very soft any rough surface in the floor may injury the piglet and during winter avoid cold exposure using straw or grass bedding (Alarcon *et al.*,2021).

Farrowing pen Bar-Separation of piglet from sow during night to avoid crushing. Anti-crushing metal bar may be fitted at the sow pen so that sow can lay down at the creep area and also restrain the sow for first few days so minimum contact with piglets (Nicolaisen, *et al*, 2019). Unfed and inanition can be avoided with proper feeding and use of milk replacer.

Conclusion: Piglet mortality is a big threat to pig farming, high mortality more than 10% is economically detrimental. Care must be taken to tackle the risk factors and aetiology. The preventive measures must be taken well in advance before farrowing as well as round the year in the farm so that the piglet mortality remains below 10%.

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